

**ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF LEARNING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES THROUGH ONLINE PLATFORMS**

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Abstract: This article is about the advantages and disadvantages of learning foreign languages through online platforms. Based on scientific data, the author analyzed the problem on the basis of existing literature and studied the specific aspects of learning foreign languages through online platforms.

Keywords: Foreign language, media, internet, platform, student.

A foreign language is a subject that, due to its uniqueness (creating an artificial language environment for students due to the absence of a natural language), includes the most flexible and extensive use of various technical teaching tools. Therefore, it is not surprising that the new opportunities provided by multimedia tools have found wide applications in foreign language teaching.

Of course, multimedia tools play the main role here. But first of all, I would like to say a few words about simple multimedia documents and presentations (Power Point) that the teacher can prepare in Microsoft Word. They are easy to implement and apply, but they play a big role in making the lesson more active and emotionally impacting the students.

The advantage of Word documents is their relatively small size and ease of creation. The teacher can develop them for specific situations, topics and groups with an infinite variety of options. At the same time, such documents do not lose the advantages of multimedia: they are bright, colorful, allow students to work individually and expand work opportunities.

For example, the electronic version of the test allows students to move objects in the document, place them in the right places, delete them, group them according to the task, insert the necessary items, etc.

Unfortunately, only a few computer science teachers can boast of programming skills; teachers of other subjects often have computers at the average amateur user level. However, some simple tricks allow us to introduce elements of self-control here, in, say, a validation test. For example, students are given a test with blank spaces or tables where they have to write their answers. The completed

test is printed on a printer or on a floppy disk for evaluation by the teacher, after which the students are asked to press the button with non-printable symbols and check your answers with the buttons printed in this mode hidden text. Of course, it is not always possible to use this method, but in another test you can password protect the key input, give the password only after the independent work is submitted for verification, turn the text of the keys white and highlight certain lines after the work is completed and suggest changing text color, etc.

The value of presentations created by the teacher is that the material in them is given to students in a concise, correct sequence; there is nothing superfluous in it, everything works to achieve the goals and objectives of a specific lesson, unlike ready-made films and slides. In addition, for the presentation, you can put the text that best suits the topic of the lesson from an informative and lexical point of view. When viewing the presentation again, the text can be deleted, and the students are given the task of speaking out the slides independently. Thus, the teacher gets rid of the need to adapt the ready-made text for students and spend valuable class time on the noise that is almost inevitable when using ready-made presentations; moreover, the timing of the presentation material is clear.

But, of course, multimedia tools have the strongest impact on students. They have become the objective reality of our time, and a foreign language teacher cannot help but use the opportunities they offer to teach real communication in a foreign language. Together with them, new forms and methods of education, a new ideology of thinking enter the school. According to the previously adopted teaching model at the school:

in the educational technology center - teacher;

there is unconditional competition among students;

students play a passive role in the class;

The essence of learning is the transfer of knowledge (facts).

The new educational model that replaces it is based on the following principles:

student at the educational technology center;

in the center of educational activity - cooperation;

students play an active role in learning;

the essence of technology is the development of self-learning ability and communicative competence of listeners.

The main groups of tasks solved with the help of multimedia include:

supporting students' learning;

ensuring real communication with native speakers;

providing access to all participants of the educational process from rapidly growing information funds stored in centralized information systems; ensuring mutual cooperation of teachers, exchange of pedagogical experience and didactic materials.

The most convenient multimedia tool should be called an electronic textbook. According to the type of organization and the method of delivery to the student, there are three types of multimedia textbooks:

- on CD-ROM with a printed insert or printed;
- on Internet sites with or without a printed application;
- On CD-ROM, but linked to some Internet sites with or without a printed supplement.

Why are multimedia (electronic) textbooks so attractive for teachers and students? The fact is that the knowledge that provides a high level of professional competence is always subject to rapid changes. Electronic textbooks make it possible to monitor these changes and thereby provide high-level training of specialists.

Advantages of electronic textbooks:

Visual presentation of the material (using color, pictures, sound, video, animation, etc.).

Quick feedback (built-in test systems provide quick control over the mastery of the material).

Interactive mode allows students to control the speed of the learning material).

The ability to regularly update the textbook as new information becomes available (the electronic textbook is located in a certain place in the virtual space, and millions of people have access to it; to add or correct something, it is enough to change one . file and tomorrow millions of people will have an edited version of the old textbook).

Ease of use.

Disadvantages of currently available electronic textbooks:

Failure to take into account the age characteristics of the announced range of students.

Absence links to specific lexical and grammatical material of the program in which the student is engaged.

Study only 1-2 lexical topics in each textbook and the lack of a textbook series that respects the continuity of lexical and grammatical material.

Opportunities for group and teamwork are limited.

Lack of real communication that can't even be programmed interactively.

These shortcomings do not allow the use of electronic textbooks as the main educational tool, especially in school, and the assistant mainly assigns an educational task to them.

In this sense, telecommunications has a wide range of opportunities, although due to technical and methodological problems that have not yet been resolved, its role is currently modest. But online classes with the help of a network do not seem fantastic. Similar experimental trainings are conducted by teachers of some higher educational institutions for their branches and basic preparatory educational institutions in remote settlements; ratings of such classes are quite high.

Teachers now use telecommunications primarily for extracurricular activities with students in selected pilot projects as an adjunct to existing courses and subjects.

Modern society places high demands on education and the overall development of students, the effectiveness of mastering the program. Every child should be taught to receive, process, evaluate and use a large amount of information in a short period of time. It is very important to organize the educational process in such a way that the child works actively, with interest and enthusiasm in the lesson, sees the results of his work and is able to evaluate them independently.

A combination of traditional teaching methods and modern information technologies, including computers using Internet resources, helps the teacher to solve this difficult task. The use of a computer in the classroom allows to make the learning process mobile, strictly differentiated, individual and interactive.

A modern computer combines the capabilities of a television, a VCR, a book, a calculator, and a telephone. . This method of teaching is also very attractive for teachers: it helps to correctly assess the child's abilities and knowledge, encourages them to look for new, non-traditional forms and methods of teaching, opens a wide path to pedagogical creativity. At the same time, the computer does not replace the teacher, but complements him, and when used correctly, plays the role of a tool that significantly increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical process.

With the widespread use of computer networks in educational institutions and at home, schoolchildren and teachers had the opportunity to quickly get the necessary information from anywhere in the world. Global information resources can be accessed instantly through the global telecommunications network.

English, like any other language, has a communicative function, therefore, as an academic subject, it is both a goal and a means of learning. Several billion English-language multimedia files containing educational, methodological and scientific information have been published on the Internet, which makes it possible to organize rapid consulting support, model research activities and conduct virtual training sessions (seminars) in real time. , lectures).

In preparation for the lesson, English language teachers have the opportunity to use materials from various local and foreign sites. The British Council conducted an online survey among teachers to find out which Internet resources are most used in teaching. Chats, online dictionaries, blogs, and virtual learning environments are among the most used teachers. 10 percent of respondents do not use the Internet in class.

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